

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL ACTIVITIES AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF PRIMARY GRADES IN SARDAB ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Parental Involvement in School Activities and Academic Performance of Primary Grades In Sardab Elementary School

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the contribution of parents' school involvement in school activities and its correlation to pupil's academic performance. The study also designed an intervention program based on the results obtained as a contribution to the Sardab Elementary School (SES) and to the locality as a whole. This aimed towards molding learners as a key to a better future. Respondents consisted of 23 male parents and 31 female parents of primary graders in SES. The study used the descriptive-correlational research design. Results showed that, parents had very low parental involvement in communicating, volunteering, and learning at home, while a low in parental involvement in parenting. Further, results revealed that parents' involvement was not significantly associated to the academic performance of the pupils. This result suggested that the academic performance of pupils was not significantly associated to the parents' involvement in terms of communicating, learning at home, parenting, and volunteering. This implied that the low academic performance of the learners was due to other factors and not by the parents involvement. With that, the researcher designed an intervention that would solve the problem holistically involving collaboration of principals, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders. The intervention program happened gradually but would surely provide a good results if the proper collaboration is made.

Keywords: *parental involvement, academic performance, school involvement*

Introduction

Parent's involvement in young children's education has many aspects. Parents are considered to be most important primary role models in their young children's immediate surroundings. Assuring their children's academic achievement and success in schools is one of the most important aspirations of every parent in every culture. The extent of parents' school involvement in school diminishes as the child gets older. Various studies had shown that active parents' involvement in their children's education declines the older, the children become. In most cases, their involvement is extensively observed in pre-school days only. Meanwhile, in the rural areas, they trained their children how to be independent at an early age. To some extent, this kind of parenting has a bad effect on the child's development because they were not yet prepared to accept deep responsibilities.

Parental involvement was an important issue. This might positively or negatively influence children's education. More and more schools were aware of the importance of parent's involvement. They were encouraging families to become more involved. Due to this recent trend, it has become essential to understand what was meant by parent's involvement and what ways it has an influenced on children's education.

As a result, parents' involvement can make a difference in a child's education. Educators mostly believed that pupils performed better in school if their parents were more involved in their child's education. Pupils with parents who were involved in their school tended to have fewer behavioral problems and better academic performance. Involvement allowed parents to monitor school and classroom activities. They should coordinate their effort with teachers to encourage acceptable classroom behavior and ensure that the child completed the schoolwork. Generally, parents had direct impact on their children's progress in school.

According to Garcia and Thornton (2014) ongoing research showed that family engagement in schools improved student achievement, reduced absenteeism, and restored parents' confidence in their children's education. Pupils with involved parents or other caregivers earned higher grades and test scores. They had also better social skills and showed improved behavior. With the above presentations, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study, which related to the effect of parents' involvement in school activities towards the academic performance of the pupils. This study would be conducted to assess the parent's involvement in school activities and academic performance of grade II learners in Sardab Elementary School.

As a DepEd public teacher for four years, the researcher values and acknowledges DepEd's main mission, which was to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality education, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education. Teachers facilitated learning and constantly nurture every learner and family, community, and other stakeholders. They were actively engaged and shared responsibility for developing life-long learners. The researcher observed that, mostly, in rural areas parents involvement were less observed. Follow-ups of grades were usually neglected by parents since they focused more on their means of living.

As noticed by the researcher, there were many reasons from the parents and also from the schools for their lack of involvement to the learners. Sometimes parents felt unwelcomed in school, lack of knowledge and education, and might not feel that education was important. They often feel that they were not needed in school and their suggestions might not be significant and disparaging. Some parents might be busy at work, more likely, there was a shortage of time. Embarrassment was another factor also of lack of parental

involvement in different school activities. The parents might be illiterate or they were not confident to speak with school administrators because they felt inferior. This could make communication difficult if not impossible.

As observed by the researcher also, some pupils were having difficulty mainly in the following three subjects like English, Science, and Math. Reading and comprehension skills were also prominent problems in the school.

It was therefore in this context that the researcher was vent on studying to determine the effect of parents' school involvement to pupils' academic performance in Sardab Elementary School, during this school year 2019-2020. As a concerned teacher of Sardab Elementary School who perceives education to play an important role in building our nation to higher heights, the researcher aimed to contribute on producing quality learners that possess the 21st century skills of today's learners. This was possible if effective and efficient quality teaching performance from teachers supplement with active partnership from parents.

Research Questions

The study generally aimed to determine the contribution of parents' school involvement in school activities which correlated on pupils' academic performance at Sardab Elementary School, East II District, and Division of Iligan City during school year 2019-2020.

Specifically, this endeavor sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the extent of parental involvement in school activities in the following dimensions
 - 1.1 parenting;
 - 1.2 communicating;
 - 1.3 volunteering; and
 - 1.4 learning at home?
2. What is the academic performance of the pupils?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the parents' school involvement in school activities and the academic performance of the pupils?
4. What intervention program can be devised based on the result of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive-correlational method of research was applied in this study. The research design was appropriate in determining the level of parental involvement of the parent respondents and its relationship to the academic performance of the primary graders of Sardab Elementary School.

Respondents

The primary grade parents at Sardab Elementary School in Digkilaan, Iligan City during the school year 2019-2020 served as respondents of the study. Respondents were consisted of 23 males, and 31 females with a total of fifty-four (54).

Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was the researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire was constructed after reading various literatures and studies regarding parental involvement. Some relevant feedbacks of parents from the school based management questionnaire was also modified. The first, second, and third grading average of the sixty-eight primary graders were utilized in order to get the reliability coefficient.

This study used the four-point scale with four (4), as very high mark, three (3), as the high mark, two (2), as the low, and one (1), as the last and low mark. There were four parts of the questionnaire with statement that were rated by the parents.

Procedure

Data gathering underwent different processes. First, a letter of recommendation for the researcher to conduct her study was taken from the adviser and noted by the Dean of the Graduate Studies, St. Peter's College, Iligan City. With the letter, the researcher proceeded to the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Iligan City to ask permission to administer the questionnaire. Given the permission, the researcher then went to the District Supervisor's Office and the Principal informing them of the researcher's intention to conduct the study.

The researcher together with the advisers on each grade level asked the parents of the primary graders to attend the homeroom meeting or on the card day. There were 54 respondents, 23 males and 31 females. Before the distribution of the questionnaire, the purpose of conducting the study was explained thoroughly. The confidentiality of their responses to the questionnaires was assured. In addition, a brief instruction on how to fill the questionnaire was also demonstrated. All questionnaires were collected immediately as soon as the respondents finished accomplishing them. For those illiterate respondents, the researcher conducted an interview type on them.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were utilized after the tally and the classifying of data.

For problems 1 and 3, Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the socio-economic profile of the participants.

For problem 2, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the level of parental involvement.

For problem 4, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used to find the significant relationships between the parental involvement levels and the socio-economic profile of the participants; and to find the relationships between the academic performance of the primary graders and the levels of parental involvement.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, discusses, and interprets the data collected based on the experiments performed in the study.

Problem 1. What is the extent of parental involvement in school activities in terms of parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, and decision-making?

Table 1. *Extent of Parental Involvement in School Activities in Terms of Parenting*

<i>Parenting</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
P1. Set a regular time for my child to study	1.61±0.74	Very Low
P2. Establish a quiet place at home for my child to study	1.56±0.66	Very Low
P3. Monitor my child's homework	1.21±0.53	Very Low
P4. Control my child's television viewing habits	1.11±0.42	Very Low
P5. Make sure that my child has excellent attendance at school	3.75±0.43	Very High
P6. Explain to my child the importance of good education	2.19±0.80	Low
P7. Ask my child what happened at school each day	1.78±0.79	Low
P8. Inform my child about the school's discipline plan	1.56±0.69	Very Low
P9. Strengthen my child's learning by providing nutritious meals and adequate time for sleep	3.42±0.69	Very High
Average	2.01±0.24	Low

Note: 1.00-1.74 – Very Low, 1.75-2.49 – Low, 2.50-3.24 – High, 3.25-4.00 – Very High

Table 1 presents the extent of parental involvement in school activities in terms of parenting. Result showed that the parents had low parenting involvement in explaining to their child the importance of good education ($M=2.19$, $SD=0.80$) and asking their child what happened at school each day ($M=1.78$, $SD=0.79$). Additionally, the parents' engagement in creating a quiet study space for their child at home was quite low ($M=1.56$, $SD=0.66$), monitoring their child's homework ($M=1.21$, $SD=0.53$), and controlling their child's television viewing habits ($M=1.11$, $SD=0.42$). However, the parents had very high parenting involvement in strengthening their child's learning by providing nutritious meals and adequate time to sleep ($M=3.42$, $SD=0.69$). As a result, the parents' involvement in school and home activities was often limited. It suggested that the parents' involvement in their kids' academic pursuits was not their top priority.

According to Bennett (2012), parental disengagement was bad for a child's growth and development. According to Marti et al. (2018), there was a substantial correlation between increased parent involvement and improvements in their children's early reading, numeracy, and self-regulation skills. Furthermore, Cadosales et al. (2017) reported that students appreciated the time their parents spent shopping with them for project and performance-related materials, their presence when cards were distributed, and their methods of punishment. It was advised that parents make time to instruct their kids, supporting them in meeting deadlines and learning how to deal with receiving failing marks. Parents needed to go to workshops on how to spend quality time with their children and how to motivate them. It was advised to improve the rapport between parents and teachers. Cooperation between parents and children should be emphasized more in school activities.

Table 2. *Extent of Parental Involvement in School Activities in Terms of Communicating*

<i>Communicating</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
C1. Receive messages and information from school through television/cellphone of any school related activities.	1.04±0.19	Very Low
C2. Regularly read the school newsletter	1.00±0.00	Very Low
C3. Attend parent/teacher Conference	2.17±0.95	Low
C4. Initiate contact with my child's teacher or principal just to show my support	1.85±0.86	Low
C5. Attend school special events (Culmination Programs, Buwan ng Wika, Nutrition Day).	1.44±0.57	Very Low
C6. Familiarize with the grading scale used on my child's report card.	1.63±0.66	Very Low
Average	1.52±0.21	Very Low

Note: 1.00-1.74 – Very Low, 1.75-2.49 – Low, 2.50-3.24 – High, 3.25-4.00 – Very High

Table 2 presents the extent of parental involvement in school activities in terms of communicating. Results showed that parents had very low parenting involvement in receiving messages and information from school through television/cellphone of any school related activities ($M=1.04$, $SD=0.19$), reading the school newsletter ($M=1.00$, $SD=0.00$), attending school special events (Culmination Programs, Buwan ng Wika, Nutrition Day) ($M=1.44$, $SD=0.57$), and familiarizing the grading scale used on my child's report card ($M=1.63$, $SD=0.66$). Furthermore, a low parenting involvement in attending parent/teacher conference ($M=2.17$, $SD=0.95$) and in

initiating contact with my child’s teacher or principal just to show my support (M=1.85, SD=0.86). Thus, on the average, the parents had low parenting engagement in school activities in terms of communicating. They were not into committing themselves in different school activities and this was because of many various reasons like lack of time. They were more into finding food for their family and be able to survive and continue their life.

Schools need to realize, according to Dixon (1992), that parents' absence from the classroom did not always imply that they were failing in their duties. It's possible that they were just too busy, too poor, or too ignorant to assist. Parents frequently didn't feel accepted at school. They believed they had nothing valuable or significant to contribute. It's also possible that parents don't think the school is interested in learning anything about them. This was particularly valid in situations when the parent may not have had extensive schooling.

Table 3. *Extent of Parental Involvement in School Activities in Terms of Volunteering*

<i>Volunteering</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
V1. Coach a sport team	1.26±0.56	Very Low
V2. Adviser of club activity	1.07±0.26	Very Low
V3. Offer to assist on school trip	1.65±0.65	Very Low
V4. Serve on school council	1.74±0.78	Very Low
V5. Help organize a school event	1.78±0.77	Low
V6. Participate as a classroom volunteer	1.89±0.60	Very Low
V7. Assist in planning graduation activities	1.24±0.58	Very Low
V8. Help to run a fund raising event	2.11±0.66	Low
V9. Assist in nutrition program	2.78±0.88	High
Average	1.72±0.22	Very Low

Note: 1.00-1.74 – Very Low, 1.75-2.49 – Low, 2.50-3.24 – High, 3.25-4.00 – Very High

Table 3 presents the extent of parental involvement in school activities in terms of volunteering. Results showed that parents had very low parental involvement in coaching a sport team (M=1.26, SD=0.56), advising of club activity (M=1.07, SD=0.26), offering to assist on school trip (M=1.65, SD=0.65), serving on school council (M=1.74, SD=0.78), participating as a classroom volunteer (M=1.89, SD=0.60), and assisting in planning graduation activities (M=1.24, SD=0.58). While a low parenting involvement was obtained in helping organized a school event (M=1.78, SD=0.77) and helping to run a fund raising event (M=2.11, SD=0.66). The result also revealed a high parental involvement in assisting in nutrition program (M=2.78, SD=0.88). Thus, on the average, the parents had low parenting involvement in school activities in terms of volunteering except in assisting in nutrition program. This implied that although parents had low involvement in school activities in terms of volunteering. However, they were of great concern in assuring that their child had obtained good nutrition.

Embarrassment was another factor in inactivity, according to Brink and Chandler (1993). It's possible that neither parent speaks English fluently or is literate. It could be difficult or impossible to communicate as a result. Memories of the parent's academic failings were another cause of humiliation. Being reminded of his own shortcomings in that location would not be a place the father would particularly want to go back to.

Table 4. *Extent of Parental Involvement in School Activities in Terms of Learning at Home*

<i>Learning at Home</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
L1. Help my child develop reading skills	1.17±0.42	Very Low
L2. Help my child develop writing skills	1.30±0.57	Very Low
L3. Help my child develop mathematical skills	1.65±0.83	Very Low
L4. Assist my child in preparing for tests/examinations	1.96±0.67	Low
L5. Monitor homework to ensure that assignments are completed on time and done to the best of my child’s ability	1.19±0.48	Very Low
L6. Obtain outside educational support to assist with learning at home (i.e., tutoring, homework club)	1.08±0.27	Very Low
Average	1.39±0.22	Very Low

Note: 1.00-1.74 – Very Low, 1.75-2.49 – Low, 2.50-3.24 – High, 3.25-4.00 – Very High

Table 4 presents the extent of parental involvement in school activities in terms of learning at home. Results showed that parents had very low parental involvement in helping their child developed reading skills (M=1.17, SD=0.42), helping their child developed writing skills (M=1.30, SD=0.57), helping their child developed mathematical skills (M=1.65, SD=0.83), monitoring homework to ensure that assignments were completed on time and done to the best of their child’s ability (M=1.19, SD=0.48), and obtaining outside educational support to assist with learning at home (i.e., tutoring, homework club) (M=1.08, SD=0.27). While a low parental involvement obtained in assisting their child in preparing for tests/examinations (M=1.96, SD=0.67). Thus, on the average, the parents had low parenting involvement in school activities in terms of learning at home. This implied that even at home the parents did not have any involvement spent to helping their children accomplished all the academic activities.

According to Vandergrift and Greene (1992), it's probable that the dad wasn't really interested in the school or his child's education. The parent may not think that education was necessary.

Table 5 presents the consolidated findings of extent of parental involvement in school activities. Results showed that parents had very low parental involvement in communicating ($M=1.52$, $SD=0.21$), volunteering ($M=1.72$, $SD=0.22$), and learning at home ($M=1.39$, $SD=0.22$), while a low in parental involvement in parenting ($M=2.01$, $SD=0.24$). This implied that the parents were not getting themselves involved in any activities related to their child's academic performance. Thus, parents were entrusting their children fully to their teachers.

Table 5. *Consolidated Findings of Extent of Parental Involvement in School Activities*

<i>Extent of Parental Involvement</i>	<i>Mean ± SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Parenting	2.01±0.24	Low
Communicating	1.52±0.21	Very Low
Volunteering	1.72±0.22	Very Low
Learning at Home	1.39±0.22	Very Low
Total Measure	1.66±0.13	Very Low

Note: 1.00-1.74 – Very Low, 1.75-2.49 – Low, 2.50-3.24 – High, 3.25-4.00 – Very High

According to LaBahn (1995), parental involvement was a combination of the parent's dedication and active involvement in the student's education as well as the school. There were numerous issues with participation. Simply put, a lot of schools were clueless about how to address the non-traditional family and the issues it raised. Parents may not have believed that education was necessary, felt uncomfortable at school, or lacked information and education. There were a lot of options available for enhancing parental participation. The school principal's complete commitment was of utmost importance. When things were put into practice, solutions. The effects were great, especially for the pupils. It improved pupil's achievement which was the key objective.

Problem 2. What is the academic performance of the pupils?

Table 6. *Academic Performance of the Pupils*

<i>Ranges of Grades</i>	<i>Performance Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
90-100	Outstanding	0	0.0
85-89	Very Satisfactory	0	0.0
80-84	Satisfactory	19	35.2
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	35	64.8
≤ 74	Did not meet expectations	0	0.0
Total		54	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 78.63 (2.29) Minimum (Maximum) = 75 (83)

Table 6 presents the academic performance of the pupils. Results showed that performance levels of the learners were only in the satisfactory (35.2%) and fairly satisfactory (64.8%) levels. A zero percentage was observed in outstanding and very satisfactory performance levels. Thus, academically, the learners had a low performance level.

According to Topor et al. (2010), parental participation was statistically significantly associated with a child's academic success, independent of the child's IQ. It has been frequently observed that a child's academic achievement is favorably correlated with the level of parental involvement in their child's education.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the parents' school involvement in school activities and the academic performance of the pupils?

Table 7. *Relationship Between the Parents' School Involvement and Academic Performance of Pupils*

<i>Parents' School Involvement</i>	<i>Academic Performance</i>		<i>Decision</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>P-value</i>		
Communicating	-0.040ns	0.774	Do not Reject Ho	Not significant
Learning at home	0.006ns	0.968	Do not Reject Ho	Not significant
Parenting	0.147ns	0.287	Do not Reject Ho	Not significant
Volunteering	0.103ns	0.457	Do not Reject Ho	Not significant
Total Measure	0.102ns	0.462	Do not Reject Ho	Not significant

Note: 1-based on Pearson Correlation ns-not significant at 0.05 level

Table 7 presents the relationship between the parents' school involvement and academic performance of the pupils using Pearson Correlation analysis. Result depicted that the parents' involvement did not significantly associate to the academic performance of the pupils ($r=0.102$, $p=0.462$). This result suggested that the academic performance of pupils was not significantly associated to the parents' involvement in terms of communicating ($p=0.774$), learning at home ($p=0.968$), parenting ($p=0.287$), and volunteering ($p=0.457$). Therefore, the null hypothesis—that there is no meaningful correlation between parents' involvement in their children's education and their academic achievement—was not rejected.

The same findings were reported by Nasri and El-Shaarawi (2006), who found that living in a crowded home and missing too many lectures had a negative impact on learners' performance. There was an absence of parent involvement to the learner's academic

activities. Nasri and El-Shaarawi (2006) further stated that non-national learners performed better than national learners. In addition, Daniyal et al. (2011) stated other factors that affected learner's academic performance, most important factors were income factor, mother and father education, family size, regularity of teachers, interest created by the teachers in the subject, and interest of the learners in the co-curricular activities.

However, this study contradicted to other different studies. Singh et al. (2016) found that learners' academic performance was positively and statistically significantly impacted by learning facilities, communication skills, and appropriate parental assistance. Furthermore, Olufemi et al. (2018) reported that parental participation has a significant impact on students' academic achievement, along with other factors like learner, school, and teacher characteristics. Additionally, it was suggested that suitable funding be allocated for educational facilities, attention, and funding for an effective teaching and learning process to occur.

Conclusions

In view of the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that parents' involvement in the academic activities, school projects and school activities still needed consistency or regularity. Teacher's effort in communicating with parents was vital in parents' participation. Parents should be given attention whenever they were in school so that they would feel welcome and would not be hesitated. Moreover, there was a need to emphasize consistency in parents' particular support in the physical needs of the children such as providing "baon" particularly their breakfast before going to school.

There were still areas in the study that needed to be worked out. Thus, the following recommendations were made.

Conduct further studies that would determine the reason of the low academic performance level of the learners.

Have continuous intervention activities that would help address the problem of the learners having a low academic performance.

Tap other government agencies for a seminar workshop regarding on responsible parenthood. Some parents would not respond to the school activities compared to agencies they were linked to with which, they could earn living. They needed to be awoken that education starts at home and they should be the first teacher to their children.

Provide program or avenue by which parents are communicated on the importance of attending meetings, of participation in school activities, involvement in school projects, initiating children to do their assignment, and do academic activities. Parents should be reminded about the importance of providing the physical needs of the children particularly providing "baon" and breakfast before going to school.

They should establish an efficient communication system where parents are able to give feedback, not only to gather reasons for not attending meetings but also to understand reasons for inconsistency of participation and involvement in school activities, school projects, and academic activities of the children.

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